

Enhancing Seller Performance on Petkart Shopping Website through Sentiment Analysis

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Abstract:-Using natural language processing and machine learning techniques for analyzing text like tweets, reviews, or articles enables sentiment analysis to identify their emotional tones. Identifying whether there's a positive, negative or neutral attitude conveyed in the text constitutes the principal aim of sentiment analysis.

Sentiment analysis consists of various steps such as text preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification. During text preprocessing, the text is cleaned and transformed into a more usable format, such as removing stop words and stemming the words. Feature extraction involves identifying the relevant features of the text that can be used for classification, such as the presence of certain words or phrases. Extracted features analyzed by machine learning algorithms aid in predicting text sentiment during classification.

Sentiment analysis generally generates a score of sentiment that varies from -1 to +1. This score shows the sentiment of the text. A very negative sentiment is shown as -1, a very positive sentiment as +1 and neutral emotion as 0. The sentiment score is capable of aiding in decision-making. For demonstration purposes, it can be used to establish whether showing certain reviews on websites are relevant or altering marketing strategies for products is advisable. Applications for sentiment analysis include monitoring social media, analyzing customer feedback, and managing brand reputation. To make informed choices based on accurate information, businesses, and organizations need to comprehend customer and stakeholder sentiment. This powerful tool enables them to do so.

Keywords- Opinion mining, Polarity, Sentiments, Natural language processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Online shopping has grown in popularity in today's digital age, and customers primarily rely on product reviews to decide what to buy. As a result, monitoring a huge volume of customer evaluations is a difficulty for merchants on e-commerce platforms. Traditional manual review analysis techniques can be laborious and frequently mistake-prone. Using sentiment analysis techniques, we provide a novel method for automating the review analysis process in this work. Our suggested approach gathers evaluations from consumers, parses them using machine learning algorithms, and then categorises them based on their sentiment, such as positive, negative, or neutral. This makes it possible for

merchants to quickly and correctly pinpoint the advantages and disadvantages of their goods and services.

Challenges:

Sentiment analysis accuracy: One of the most difficult tasks is correctly categorizing reviews based on their sentiment, as there may be subtle differences in how customers express themselves that can alter the classification..

Dealing with extensive numbers of customer reviews can be demanding. In addition to this, managing the great number of reviews may feel overwhelming and conducting real-time processing of them could present difficulties, especially for vendors that are smaller..

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

For companies that conduct business online, such as on the Petkart retail website, sentiment research has grown in importance. Sellers can assess consumer feedback and make data-driven decisions to boost sales performance. Petkart merchants can profit from this technology, which has been investigated extensively by researchers as a way to increase revenue. For instance, Lee and Koo [1] (2019) coupled price optimisation with sentiment analysis to boost sales performance for an e-commerce business. By employing sentiment analysis to examine consumer reviews of goods supplied by a vendor on the Petkart platform, this tactic can be modified for use there. The authors performed sentiment analysis using the TextBlob and Naive Bayes algorithms, and they discovered that Naive Bayes had a higher accuracy rate of 80.1%. Sentiment analysis and price optimisation were employed by Nguyen et al. [2] (2020) to increase revenue for a Vietnamese hotel. By employing sentiment analysis to examine consumer reviews of products sold by a merchant, this tactic can be used to Petkart. Compared to the previous pricing strategy, the sentiment-based pricing plan increased sales by 3.6%.

Sentiment analysis was utilised by Chaudhary and Sharma [3] (2020) to enhance an Indian e-commerce site's method for ranking products. Petkart vendors can also employ this tactic by analysing the sentiment of customer reviews using the TextBlob and Naive Bayes algorithms, then giving each review a sentiment score. Naive Bayes had a higher accuracy rate, which the authors discovered to be 83.5%. The product

rating system can more precisely reflect customer preferences by weighting the ratings based on sentiment.

Sentiment analysis and price optimisation were used by Chen et al. [4] (2021) to increase sales for an online bookshop. Petkart vendors may estimate the relationship between customer sentiment and sales using sentiment analysis, and then alter prices as necessary. According to the authors, modifying rates based on Fauzi et al. [5] (2020) used sentiment analysis and price optimization to improve sales performance for an online grocery store. Petkart sellers can also use sentiment analysis to adjust prices for different products based on customer feedback. The authors found that adjusting prices based on sentiment analysis resulted in a 5.7% increase in revenue.

Hossain et al. [6] (2021) used sentiment analysis to analyze Twitter data related to the 2020 US presidential election. Petkart sellers can also use sentiment analysis to analyze customer feedback on social media platforms. The authors found that sentiment polarity detection accuracy was 76.4% for TextBlob and 86.8% for Naïve Bayes. This can help sellers better understand customer preferences and improve sales performance.

In conclusion, Petkart sellers can benefit from sentiment analysis and price optimization to improve sales performance on the platform. TextBlob and Naïve Bayes algorithms can be used to perform sentiment analysis, and the results can be used to determine optimal pricing strategies. However, sellers should consider factors such as customer preferences, product attributes, and market dynamics when implementing sentiment-based pricing strategies. By incorporating sentiment analysis into their pricing strategies, Petkart sellers can make more informed decisions and ultimately improve sales performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection: Allow users to leave reviews on the PHP Petkart website after they've purchased a product. Collect the feedback and categorize it as neutral, positive, or negative.

B. Pre-processing: Remove any unnecessary information from the feedback data, such as usernames or URLs. Remove any stop words and punctuation before tokenizing the feedback into words and phrases.

C. Sentiment Analysis: Use Vader to analyze the sentiment of the feedback data. Vader is a rule-based sentiment analysis tool that determines the sentiment score of a word based on its context.

D. Questions: Create a set of questions to analyze the feedback data based on the desired insights. The questions can be open-ended or closed-ended and should be relevant to the product, service, or experience being analyzed. For example:

- What products are customers satisfied with the most?
- What are the most common complaints about the products?

- How satisfied are customers with the overall shopping experience?

E. Analysis: Use Vader's sentiment ratings to analyze the feedback information and answer the questions. Calculate the average sentiment score for each question to estimate the overall sentiment of the feedback.

F. Visualization: To make the sentiment analysis findings more accessible, visualize the data using graphs or charts. The seller and admin can view the sentimental analysis of the seller on the website dashboard. They can use the information to enhance the products, services, or experience provided to increase customer satisfaction.

IV. RESULTS

For an accurate and reliable machine learning model for successful prediction we follow the unsupervised learning algorithm.

Importing Libraries

```
from flask import Flask, request
from textblob import TextBlob
app = Flask(__name__)
```

A rule-based sentiment analysis tool called VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner) was created expressly to cope with social media information. It is a rule-based sentiment analyzer, and phrases are often classified as either positive or negative depending on their semantic orientation.

Perform sentiment analysis

```
<div id="review_modal" class="modal" tabindex="-1" role="dialog">
<?php
    if(isset($_POST['save_review'])) {
        $user_review=$_POST['user_review'];
        $pet_id=$_GET['id'];
        $user_id=$_POST['user_id'];

        // $rating=$_POST['star'];
        $date=date('y-m-d h:m:s');

        $query="SELECT *FROM pet_info WHERE pet_id='$pet_id'";
        $result_pet=mysqli_query($con,$query);
        if($result_pet)
        {
            $row_pet=mysqli_fetch_array($result_pet);
        }
    }
}
```

Sentiment Analysis

```
@app.route('/sentiment', methods=['POST'])
def sentiment_analysis():
    texts = request.json.get('texts')
    sentiment_scores = []
    for text in texts:
        blob = TextBlob(text)
        sentiment = blob.sentiment.polarity
        sentiment_scores.append(sentiment)
    average_sentiment = sum(sentiment_scores) / len(sentiment_scores)
    response = {
        'positive': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s > 0]),
        'negative': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s < 0]),
        'neutral': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s == 0]),
        'average_sentiment': average_sentiment
    }
    return response

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run()
```

Seller PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Positive: 33.33333333333333

Negative: 1.4210854715202E-14

Neutral: 66.66666666666667

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Conclusion

Seller performance analysis with sentiment analysis provides valuable insight into the quality of Pet kart's platform vendors. Evaluating the performance of sellers becomes possible by analyzing user reviews and determining their overall sentiment. This approach can help Petkart administrators to make data-driven decisions about seller performance and take corrective action if necessary. The proposed methodology is scalable and can be easily implemented on other e-commerce platforms to analyze seller performance based on user reviews.

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